

Studies on Indigoid Dyes. Part II. Benzylidene-2-(5-iodo)thionaphthene

Arun Kumar Sinha

The effect of an iodine atom, when present in 5-position of the benzene nucleus of thionaphthene ring, has been studied with regard to benzaldehyde series. For this purpose four new dyes have been synthesised by condensing the 5-iodothioindoxyl with benzaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, and *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde. Their dyeing and other properties have been studied.

Attempt has been made to explain the difficulty in vatting from the view point of ionic mechanism. These dyes are feeble but definite sensitisers. The absorption maxima and sensitisation spectra of these dyes are reported.

In previous communications, the properties of the dyes produced by condensation of 5-iodothioindoxyl with isatin, acenaphthenequinone, phenanthraquinone, and their substituted products have been studied¹.

The present investigation was carried out with a view to studying the properties of the dyes produced by condensation of 5-iodothioindoxyl with benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehydes. Four new dyes have been synthesised by condensation of 5-iodothioindoxyl with benzaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, and *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde respectively.

It has been observed that except the (4'-nitro)-benzylidene-2-(5-iodo)thionaphthene, it is difficult to reduce all the dyes in alkaline hydrosulphite..

Benzylidene-2-(5-iodo)thionaphthene.

The alkaline reduction of the dyes may proceed *via* initial electron accession to the carbonyl atom, the oxygen atom picking up a proton to yield the carbinol.

1. Sinha, *this Journal*, 1954, **31**, 463; *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1956, Part III, 216,

Naturally, the electron-seeking character of the carbonyl carbon atom determines the reducibility of the dye. If now, X, is an electron-releasing group, the electron-accession requirement of the carbonyl carbon is to a large extent met by the electron relay, thus making carbonyl carbon atom less ready for electron accession from external sources.

Since the benzene nucleus itself, to some extent, and *p*-amino, or *p*-dialkylamino groups are strongly electron releasing, the difficulty encountered in the reduction of the compounds, benzylidene-2-(5-iodo)thionaphthene(P), 4'-dimethylamino benzylidene-2-(5-iodo)thionaphthene(Q), and 4'-diethylamino benzylidene-2-(5-iodo)thionaphthene(R) is easily explained.

The absorption maxima of these dyes have been determined in ethanol solution by means of a Beckman spectrophotometer, DU model, and are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Dye.	Colour in H ₂ SO ₄ .	Shade on cotton.	λ max.	Log ϵ .
Benzylidene-2-T	Brownish red	Faint pink	448 m μ	4.169
(4'-Nitro)-benzylidene-2-T	Olive-green	Light orange-yellow	462	3.798
(4'-Dimethylamino)-benzylidene-2-T	Green	Faint pink	506	4.585
(4'-Diethylamino)-benzylidene-2-T	Green	..	514	3.866

T=(5-iodo)thionaphthene.

It is, however, apparent that except in the case of 4'-nitro derivative, there has been a gradual bathochromic shift of absorption maxima with increasing molecular weights.

The dyes, when arranged in order of absorption maxima, has the sequence: 4'-NEt₂ > 4'-NMe₂ > 4'-NO₂ > 4'-H, whereas the intensities are of the order: 4'-NMe₂ > 4'-H > 4'-NEt₂ > 4'-NO₂.

Curiously enough, these dyes are photosensitisers. The resonating character of the dye molecule is probably responsible for the sensitising property. Since the dyes are non-ionic, their resonating character are, in a way, similar to those of the non-ionic sensitisers, merocyanines:

The sensitising spectra of the dyes were determined by means of a wedge spectrograph. The solutions of the dyes were made in absolute ethanol. The solution of the dyes (1 : 2000) was further diluted (1 : 50,000) with 60% ethanol. As the 4'-nitrobenzylidene derivative was not so soluble in ethanol, the sensitisation spectra could not be determined by the usual process. The sensitisation spectra of these dyes are shown in Fig. 1. For the sake of comparison, the sensitisation spectrograph of an unbathed process plate is appended in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

The extra-sensitisation conferred by the dyes are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Symbol of dye.	Extra-sensitisation.	
	Range.	Maxima.
P	3460-5500 Å	4500 Å
Q	3500-6040	4540
R	3460-6100	4500
Unbathed	3560-5180	4540

It is interesting to note that the diethylamino dye is a better sensitiser than its dimethylamino analogue, whereas the unsubstituted parent dye shows little extra-sensitisation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzylidene-2-(5-icdo)thionaphthene.—On heating under reflux, a solution of benzaldehyde (0.42 g.) and 5-iodothiaindoxyl (1.1 g.) in absolute ethanol (14 ml) formed a red solution. The solution on treatment with HCl (conc., 3 ml) afforded the dye as fine long needles. The refluxing was continued for further 20 minutes. The dye (0.65 g., 45%) was washed with hot water and was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid in long yellow needles, m.p. 158-59°. (Found: I, 47.9; S, 12.2. C₁₅H₉OIS requires I, 48.1; S, 12.1%).

4'-Nitrobenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)thionaphthene.—On refluxing a mixture of *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.302 g.) and 5-iodothioindoxyl (0.552 g.) in hot absolute ethanol (20 ml) and HCl (conc., 3 ml) for 10 minutes, the dye crystallised out (0.35 g., 42.8%). It was recrystallised from nitrobenzene, m.p. >300°. (Found: I, 30.9; S, 8.1. C₁₅H₈O₃NIS requires I, 31.05; S, 7.82%).

4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)thionaphthene.—*p*-Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.3 g.) and 5-iodothioindoxyl (0.57 g.) were dissolved in absolute ethanol (15 ml) and treated with HCl (conc., 2 ml), when the hydrochloride of the dye separated in yellow needles, which on washing with dilute ethanol gave a bright vermilion dye (0.3 g., 36.6%). It was purified by recrystallisation from glacial acetic acid and was obtained as long, stout, deep red needles, m.p. 227°. (Found: I, 31.3; S, 8.0. C₁₇H₁₄ONIS requires I, 31.2; S, 7.86%).

4'-Diethylaminobenzylidene-2-(5-iodo)thionaphthene.—The hydrochloride of the dye was obtained by refluxing a solution of *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.68 g.), 5-iodothioindoxyl (1.06 g.) in absolute ethanol (20 ml), and HCl (conc., 2.5 ml) for 30 minutes. The solution was cooled to 45° and was filtered. The brown product on washing with dilute ethanol (1:1) turned deep red. It was then washed with ammonium hydroxide solution and hot water. The crude dye (1 g., 60%) on recrystallisation from absolute ethanol gave red, shining, pointed needles, m.p. 164-65°. The solution of the dye is yellow in benzene, but on addition of ethanol the colour becomes red. The dye dissolves in xylene, giving a yellowish brown solution on heating and turns brownish red on cooling; in hot toluene, it produces a light yellowish brown colour which becomes deeper on cooling. (Found: I, 29.0; S, 7.4. C₁₉H₁₈ONIS requires I, 29.2; S, 7.35%).

Thanks of the author are due to Mr. M. Q. Doja, Chairman, School Examination Board, Bihar, Dr. D. P. Vidyarthi, Principal, and Dr. J. C. Banerji, Head of the Chemistry Department, B. N. College, Patna, for their kind interest and encouragement.